

4-Quinazolones: Part V. Synthesis of some Thiazolido (3,2-a) quinazolones and 5-Phenyltetrahydro-*meta*-thiazino (3,2-a) quinazolin-1,5 (6H)-dione

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Sodium borohydride has been found to reduce the cyclic imine double bond ($C=N$) in some 2-substituted 3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-ones. This reaction has been used for the synthesis of four 1-aryl-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-ones (IVa-d), 4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,5(4H)-dione (VIIa) and 5-phenyltetrahydro-*meta*-thiazino(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,6(5H)-dione (VIIb). 3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid has been cyclodehydrated to yield the anhydro compound XII.

Our interest in bridgehead nitrogen heterocycles incorporating a 4-quinazolone ring prompted us to report recently the synthesis of some imidazo(3,2-a)quinazolones¹. In this communication we describe the successful synthesis of some thiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolones: IVa-d, VIIa and XII, and the thiazino(3,2-a)quinazolone VIIb. These represent a tricyclic system with nitrogen bridgehead so far not recorded in the literature.

Sodium borohydride has been shown to reduce the imine double bond ($C=N$) in certain nitrogen heterocycles^{2,3} and therefore it was envisaged that 4-quinazolone derivatives of the type II might be reduced with sodium borohydride to III which could be easily cyclised to IV. Such a synthetic sequence has been realised in the preparation of four 1-aryl-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-ones, IVa-d. Interaction of 2-mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one⁴ (I) with appropriate phenacyl bromides in the presence of alkali

- a : Ar = Ph
 b : Ar = *p*-Br.C₆H₄
 c : Ar = *p*-MeO.C₆H₄
 d : Ar = *p*-HO.C₆H₄

1. Part II. B. D. Singh and D. N. Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 21.
2. A. I. Meyers and J. M. Greene, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1966, **31**, 556.
3. E. W. Taylor, A. McKillop and R. E. Ross., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 1990.

furnished 2-phenacylmercapto- (IIa), 2-*p*-bromophenacylmercapto- (IIb), 2-*p*-methoxyphenacylmercapto- (IIc) and 2-*p*-hydroxyphenacylmercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIId). Reduction of C = N and C = O in IIa-c was simultaneously accomplished with sodium borohydride to yield respectively 1,2-dihydro-2-(α -hydroxyphenethyl)mercapto- (IIIa), 1,2-dihydro-2-(α -hydroxy-*p*-bromophenethyl)mercapto- (IIIb) and 1,2-dihydro-2-(α -hydroxy-*p*-methoxyphenethyl)mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIIc). By the action of acetic anhydride or more conveniently with a trace of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid the reduced products IIIa-c were readily cyclodehydrated to the corresponding 1,4-diphenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (IVa), 1-*p*-bromophenyl-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (IVb) and 1-*p*-methoxyphenyl-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (IVc). But treatment of IIId with an alkaline sodium borohydride solution followed by acidification yielded the cyclised product 1-*p*-hydroxyphenyl-4-thiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (IVd) instead of the intermediate reduction product IIId. Failure to isolate IIId may be attributed to its spontaneous dehydration by the acid used for working up of the reaction mixture. Methylation of IVd with methyl iodide in DMF afforded IVc.

Again, condensation of the mercaptoquinazolone (I) with monochloroacetic acid and with ethyl bromoacetate in the presence of alkali yielded respectively 3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid and its ethyl ester (Va and Vb). Treatment of an alkaline solution of Va or of Vb with an excess of sodium borohydride at room temperature followed by acidification resulted in the separation of 4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)-quinazolin-1,5(4H)-dione (VIIa). The obvious precursor to cyclic lactam formation must be the intermediate

a : n = 1; R = H
 b : n = 1; R = Et
 c : n = 2; R = H

a : n = 1
 b : n = 2

a : n = 1
 b : n = 2

reduction product VIa, cyclisation of which proceeded only in acidic solution. In the case of Vb, the reduction of the imine bond is accompanied with the hydrolysis of the ester group caused by the alkaline reaction medium. Incidentally, 3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid (Vc), obtained by the condensation of I with β -chloropropionic acid, also underwent similar reductive cyclisation with sodium borohydride under the same reaction condition to produce 5-phenyltetrahydro-*meta*-thiazino(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,6(5H)-dione (VIIb), the formation of which must have occurred via the intermediate reduction product VIb. Taylor *et al.*³ have effected similar reductive cyclisation of 2-(2-carboxyethyl)- and 2-(3-carboxypropyl)-3(4H)quinazolone (VIIIa and VIIIb) with sodium borohydride under identical reaction condition and secured the tricyclic diamides (IXa and IXb). Both the

tricyclic quinazolones VIIa and VIIb are readily soluble in aqueous alkali and reprecipitated on acidification. Thus under basic conditions the thiazolidone and the thiazinone rings are

VIII

a : n = 2

b : n = 3

IX

a : n = 2

b : n = 3

easily cleaved. The methylene group at the 2-position (adjacent to C = O) in VIIa, unlike the 2-CH₂ group of X⁵ and XI⁶, is not activated to form 2-benzylidene derivatives. Cyclo-dehydration of the mercaptoacetic acid (Va) with a mixture of acetic anhydride and pyridine

X

XI

XII

yielded the anhydro compound XII as dark blue crystals with a bronze lusture. The meso-ionic structure XII has been assigned on the basis of the work of Duffin and Kendall⁷ who prepared and formulated similar anhydro derivatives of thiazolo(2,3-a)benzthiazole and of thiazolo(3,2-a)benzimidazole. The mercaptopropanoic acid (Ve), as expected, under the same reaction conditions did not undergo dehydration as only the unchanged material was recovered.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Phenacylmercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIa): I⁴ (6.25 g.) dissolved in 5% aq. NaOH (50 ml.) was treated with a solution of phenacyl bromide (5 g.) in acetone (20 ml.) when a colorless precipitate separated out. The mixture was diluted with water (20 ml.), cooled and the solid filtered off and washed with a little acetone. Crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave IIa as colorless needles (6 g.), m.p. 203–204°. IR(KBr) 1700 cm⁻¹ (C = O). (Found : C, 70.7; H, 4.1; N, 7.2. C₂₂H₁₆N₂O₂S requires C, 70.9; H, 4.3; N, 7.5%).

1,2-Dihydro-2-(α-hydroxyphenethyl)mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIIa): To a solution of IIa (2 g.) in diglyme (20 ml.) was added NaBH₄ (0.8 g.) dissolved in methanol (10 ml.) containing a drop of 2*N* aq. NaOH and set aside overnight. On dilution with water

4. T. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 981.

5. G. F. Duffin and J. D. Kendall, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 361.

6. J. A. Van Allan, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 24.

7. W. L. Mosby, 'Heterocyclic system with bridgehead nitrogen atoms'. Part I, Interscience Publishers, N.Y., 1961, Sec. A 128, 133.

the precipitate that separated was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol to yield IIIa as colorless needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 166–167°. IR (KBr) 3500 cm^{-1} (OH; NH), 1700 and 1630 cm^{-1} (C = O). (Found : C, 69.9; H, 5.1; N, 7.6. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 70.2; H, 5.3; N, 7.4%).

1,4-Diphenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (IVa)—*Method (a)* : IIIa (1 g.) in acetic anhydride (5 ml.) was refluxed for 15 min. and cooled when colorless crystalline material gradually deposited. It was filtered, washed with methanol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to afford IVa as colorless needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 274–275°. IR (KBr) 3200 (CH), 1750, 1660 cm^{-1} (tert. amide C = O). (Found : C, 73.5; H, 5.2; N, 7.7. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires C, 73.7; H, 5.0; N, 7.8%).

Method (b) : On heating IIIa (1 g.) dissolved in dry benzene (10 ml.) with a trace of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, fine needles separated out within 5 min. The mixture was cooled, the solid collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to furnish IVa as colorless needles (0.7 g.), m.p. 274–275°, undepressed on admixture with the specimen obtained as in (a).

2-p-Bromophenacylmercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIb) : A solution of I (6.25 g.) in 5% aq. NaOH (50 ml.) was treated with *p*-bromophenacylbromide (5.5 g.) dissolved in acetone (25 ml.) and worked up as described for the preparation of IIa. The reddish solid isolated was crystallised from glacial acetic acid to give IIb as colorless needles (6.0 g.), m.p. 198°. (Found : C, 58.8; H, 3.6; N, 6.0. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{SBr}$ requires C, 58.5; H, 3.3; N, 6.2%).

*1,2-Dihydro-2-(α -hydroxy-*p*-bromophenethyl)mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIIb)* : A solution of IIb (3 g.) in dioxan (30 ml.) was mixed with NaBH_4 (1.5 g.) dissolved in methanol (10 ml.) containing a drop of 2*N* aq. NaOH, and worked up as described for the preparation of IIIa. The product isolated on crystallisation from methanol yielded IIIb as colorless needles (2.2 g.), m.p. 173–174°. (Found : C, 58.3; H, 4.4; N, 6.3. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{SBr}$ requires C, 58.0; H, 4.1; N, 6.1%).

The methanolic mother liquor, on concentration, afforded a little colorless crystals, m.p. 275° with previous sintering at 273°, which was identified as the *cyclised product* IVb (see below) by mixed melting point.

1-p-Bromophenyl-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (IVb) : It was prepared from IIIb (1 g.) according to the methods (a) and (b) detailed for the preparation of IVa. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid to yield IVb as colorless needles : 0.5 g. by method (a); 0.7 g. by method (b), m.p. 275° with previous sintering at 273°. (Found : C, 60.7; H, 4.0; N, 6.5. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{OSBr}$ requires C, 60.4; H, 3.8; N, 6.4%).

2-p-Methoxyphenacylmercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIc) : Its preparation required the use of Na-salt of I which was obtained as follows : I (3 g.) was added portionwise with stirring to a solution of Na (0.23 g.) in dry methanol (50 ml.), undissolved I filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to give the Na-salt of I in quantitative yield, m.p. > 320°.

The Na-salt (2.5 g.) dissolved in hot methanol (25 ml.) was treated with a solution of *p*-methoxyphenacyl bromide⁸ (2.3 g.) in methanol (10 ml.) when a precipitate separated out.

8. L. C. King and G. K. Ostrum, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 3459.

After cooling, it was filtered, washed with methanol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to afford IIc as colorless needles (2 g.), m.p. 200°. (Found : C, 68.4; H, 4.6; N, 7.1. $C_{23}H_{18}N_2O_3S$ requires C, 68.6; H, 4.4; N, 6.9%).

*1,2-Dihydro-2-(α -hydroxy-*p*-methoxyphenethyl)mercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIIc)* : A solution of $NaBH_4$ (0.4 g.) in methanol (5 ml.) containing one drop of 2*N.* aq. NaOH was added to IIc (1 g.) dissolved in diglyme (20 ml.) and left overnight. The precipitate that separated after dilution with water was collected and crystallised from methanol to furnish IIIc as colorless needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 166–168°. (Found : C, 68.1; H, 5.6; N, 6.6. $C_{23}H_{22}N_2O_3S$ requires C, 67.9; H, 5.4; N, 6.8%).

*1-p-Methoxyphenyl-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-*a*)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (IVc)* : It was obtained from IIIc (1 g.) according to method (b) described for the preparation of IVa. Crystallisation from glacial acetic acid gave IVc as colorless needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 260–261°. (Found : C, 71.4; H, 5.4; N, 7.1. $C_{23}H_{20}N_2O_2S$ requires C, 71.1; H, 5.1; N, 7.2%).

2-p-Hydroxyphenylmercapto-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IIId) : A solution of *p*-hydroxyphenacyl bromide⁸ (1 g.) in methanol (10 ml.) was added to Na-salt of I (1.35 g.) dissolved in hot methanol (20 ml.) when a crystalline precipitate separated out. After cooling the solid was filtered, washed with methanol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to yield IIId as colorless needles (1.2 g.), m.p. 239–240°. (Found : C, 68.3; H, 4.4; N, 7.5. $C_{22}H_{16}N_2O_3S$ requires C, 68.0; H, 4.1; N, 7.2%).

*1-p-Hydroxyphenyl-4-phenylthiazolido(3,2-*a*)quinazolin-5(4H)-one (IVd)* : Powdered $NaBH_4$ (0.8 g.) was gradually added to a solution of IIId (2 g.) in *N*-aq. NaOH (40 ml.) and left overnight. It was cooled, acidified with conc. HCl and the solid that separated was filtered and washed with water. Crystallisation from methanol afforded the cyclised product IVd as colorless needles (1.2 g.), m.p. 278–279°. (Found : C, 70.7; H, 5.0; N, 7.6. $C_{22}H_{18}N_2O_2S$ requires C, 70.5; H, 4.8; N, 7.4%).

A solution of IVd (0.5 g.) in DMF (10 ml.) was treated with CH_3I (1 ml.) and K_2CO_3 (1 g.) and left overnight. Dilution with water and cooling gave a precipitate which was filtered and washed with water. On crystallisation from glacial acetic acid furnished IVc as colorless needles (0.3 g.) m.p. and mixed m.p. 260–261°.

3-Phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetic acid (Va) : I (3.3 g.) dissolved in NaOH solution (1.7 g. NaOH in 10 ml. water and 20 ml. DMF) was treated with monochloroacetic acid (4 g.) dissolved in Na_2CO_3 solution (3.5 g. Na_2CO_3 , 10 H_2O in 15 ml. water and 10 ml. DMF) and heated on steam bath for 2 hr. It was diluted with water (100 ml.), cooled and acidified with conc. HCl to yield a precipitate. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to give Va as colorless needles (3.5 g.), m.p. 210°. IR(KBr) 3200 broad (acid OH; CH), 1750 (acid C = O), 1660 cm^{-1} (tert. amide C = O). (Found : C, 61.7; H, 4.1; N, 9.1. $C_{16}H_{12}N_2O_3S$ requires C, 61.5; H, 3.8; N, 8.9%).

Ethyl 3-Phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptoacetate (Vb) : A solution of I (5 g.) in DMF (20 ml.), ethyl bromoacetate (2.5 ml.) and K_2CO_3 (14 g.) were heated on steam bath for 2 hr. with occasional shaking. The mixture was poured into water and the precipitate that separated was filtered after cooling. Crystallisation from methanol yielded Vb as rosetts

of needles (4 g.), m.p. 165–166°. (Found : C, 63.3; H, 5.0; N, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{16}N_2O_3S$ requires C, 63.5; H, 4.7; N, 8.2%).

4-Phenylthiazolido(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,5(4H)-dione (VIIa) : (i) A solution of Va (1 g.) in *N* aq. NaOH (10 ml.) was treated with $NaBH_4$ (0.4 g.) in water (5 ml.) and left overnight. The clear solution was acidified with 6*N*. H_2SO_4 and the precipitate that separated was filtered, washed successively with water, aq. $NaHCO_3$ and water. Crystallisation from glacial acetic acid furnished VIIa as clusters of colorless needles (0.65 g.), m.p. 277–278°. IR(KBr) 3200 (CH), 1750 (ring fused γ -lactam C = O), 1670 cm^{-1} (tert. amide C = O). (Found : C, 65.0; H, 4.3; N, 9.2. $C_{16}H_{12}N_2O_2S$ requires C, 64.8; H, 4.0; N, 9.4%).

(ii) To Vb (1 g.) dissolved in diglyme (15 ml.) was added a solution of $NaBH_4$ (0.4 g.) in methanol (10 ml.) and the clear alkaline solution was left overnight. A little crystalline solid (0.1 g.), m.p. 275–276°, separated out which was filtered off and identified as VIIa by mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen. The filtrate, on acidification with dil. HCl, gave a precipitate which was collected, washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid to afford VIIa as colorless needles (0.5 g.), m.p. and mixed m.p. 277–278°.

3-Phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one-2-mercaptopropionic acid (Vc) : A solution of I (3.3 g.) in NaOH solution (1.7 g. NaOH in 10 ml. water and 20 ml. DMF) was treated with β -chloropropionic acid (4.53 g. dissolved in aq. Na_2CO_3 (3.5 g. Na_2CO_3 , 10 H_2O in 15 ml. water) and worked up as described for the preparation of Va. The product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid to furnish Vc as colorless prismatic needles (4 g.), m.p. 200–201°. (Found : C, 62.3; H, 4.5; N, 8.6. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_3S$ requires C, 62.5; H, 4.3; N, 8.5%).

5-Phenyltetrahydro-meta-thiazino(3,2-a)quinazolin-1,6(5H)-dione (VIIb) : Vc (1 g.) dissolved in *N*. NaOH aq. (10 ml.) was treated with a solution of $NaBH_4$ (0.4 g.) in water (5 ml.) and worked up as method (i) described for the preparation of VIIa. The product isolated was crystallised from glacial acetic acid to give VIIb as colorless needles (0.6 g.), m.p. 272–273°. (Found : C, 65.6; H, 4.3; N, 9.3. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_2S$ requires C, 65.8; H, 4.5; N, 9.0%).

Anhydro compound (XII) : Va (1 g.) dissolved in pyridine (10 ml.) was treated with acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and heated on steam bath when within 5 min. blue crystalline precipitate separated out. It was filtered, washed with a little ethanol and crystallised from ethanol to furnish the anhydro compound XII as blue needles with a bronze lustre (0.56 g.), m.p. > 300°. (Found : C, 65.4; H, 3.7; N, 9.7. $C_{16}H_{10}N_2O_2S$ requires C, 65.3; H, 3.4; N, 9.5%).

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